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THE IMPORTANCE OF TOURISTIC ROUTES AND THEIR BRIEF HISTORY

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ABSTRACT

In this article, information on touristic routes are described and people as well as scholars who contributed to this was referred. Moreover, in the article also was described works which were done for new uncreated routes and destinations.

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The development of tourist routes to the tourist facility is of great importance in providing jobs for local labor resources. Currently, the use of tourist resources of religious shrines for tourism purposes is developing. This development is mainly due to the increase in the number of visits of local and international tourists to places where religious leaders are buried in cities and district centers.

The next task is to intensify the development of tourist routes to the shrines, mausoleums and shrines of famous religious leaders, saints, lords and sayyids in local areas. Due to the lack or unsatisfactory condition of tourist services in such places in the districts, local tourism development programs are implemented very slowly. However, the creation of tourist routes for employment of the local population is one of the most economically promising ways to develop tourism.

Another important aspect of the creation of tourist routes is that the increase in the flow of tourists on the tourist route will create a network of acquaintances, friendships and cooperation between countries, peoples and nations in both domestic and international tourism. So far, such friendly relations are mainly between urban residents and foreigners. The main reason for this is that we have not yet been able to attract foreign tourists to natural areas, landscapes, nature reserves or reservoirs outside our cities.

According to current data, 64% of Uzbekistan's territory is desert and hilly. There are currently 55 registered tourist resources in the region. It is certain that these resources are on 14 separate topics, and that the vast desert nature, the life of the desert people, the flora and fauna of the desert can be used to develop local tourism and international tourism comes. As mentioned above, these tourist routes will definitely include service areas, maintenance, tent seasonal camps, exotic excursions (on camels, horses, donkeys, carts). National food outlets will be established. Naturally, all of these services are provided by locals.

Second, because the desert areas are far from the city and district centers, tourists will definitely stay overnight. If the famous "black houses" of the desert people (felt) are invited to spend the night, any tourist (even local tourists) will stay there for at least 1-2 days due to his curiosity (perhaps for the first time).

Both international and local tourists will meet and make friends with locals during these 1-2 days. The hospitality, curiosity, etc. human qualities of our people attract tourists, It is clear that there will be exchanges of information between the countries, and so on. The emergence of such friendly relations, the knowledge of people, information about countries, of course, expands the human mind, creates a feeling of a different view of the world.

From the above, it can be concluded that the start of the development of tourist routes to all tourist resources in the country will be the most important economic factor in the development of tourism.

The study of the theoretical foundations of the development of tourist routes to tourist resources also puts on the agenda the creation of a state program for the use of tourism resources.

The role and importance of the development of tourist routes in the life of the country requires us to take into account that there are great opportunities. In the current development of tourism, the issues of creating and improving the infrastructure of tourism services are also on the agenda.

In many cases, tourism organizations, travel agencies and even tourism management organizations prioritize the creation of tourist resources, the infrastructure that initially serves tourists in tourist facilities.

That fact must be taken into account. "

History of tourism Experts have different approaches to the problems of tourism and focus on assistance. Many see tourism as a new phenomenon, both in the economy and in the movement of humanity around the world. The fact that the other side's origins are from the fact that tourism has traveled around the world in the past also makes up many scholars. However, modern theories of tourism suggest that neither the world's first travelers nor source trips have anything to do with tourism. In the opinion of such loading visitors, the first travelers did not go on the trip of their own free will. These trips were productive and did not recognize freedom. Their goal was to open new commercial markets, new lands, to subjugate peoples by force, to spread religion, and so on.

In the practice of foreign countries, it has become an international practice where the crimes of bribery of officials are widespread. In some countries, it was even possible to get deductions from your company's tax liabilities in exchange for bribes, and this is not surprising, as multinational corporations around the world have already paid bribes to support their businesses.¹

The terms "tourism" and "tourist" began to be written in the scientific literature in the late seventeenth century and began to be widely used in the nineteenth century, gaining their current definition internationally in the 1960s. It is believed that the first voyage in the world was organized by the ancient Egyptian queen Hetshepsut in 1501-1448 BC. Also in 2000 BC, the Egyptian Sinuhit recorded his journey to the East (Eden) in his Sinuhit Travels. There have been many such trips in the past. Below we will focus on the journeys that took place on the threshold of our era and beyond, and the routes of these journeys.

Article covers the facts connected with life, scientific activities and socio-political views of the great thinkers and statesmen of Central Asia living in a wound of East Renaissance, more precisely in the 9-12th centuries and during board of temurid (the 14-15th centuries).²

Muhammad ibn Musa al-Khwarizmi (780-847). The first prominent figure in the Khorezm School of Science was Muhammad Khorezmi, who, in the words of the American orientalist D. Sarton, was "one of the greatest mathematicians of all time." Muhammad Khorezmi was born in Khorezm and died in Baghdad.

Al-Khwarizmi's works contain a total of 537 names of places, cities, mountains (203 names), seas and islands, and finally rivers.

His travels include names such as the Red Sea, Indian and Atlantic Oceans. The Azov Sea and the Nile Basin were also commented on. The Italian orientalist K. Nallino wrote: "No other nation in Europe had achieved the success of Al-Khwarizmi and was not able to create such a work." Al-Khwarizmi's geographical ideas, which he developed as a result of his travels, raised this science to a new level and led to the creation of a new geography in the east in the early 9th century.

Routes of foreign travelers were also considered relative. Because it is impossible to list all the trips of foreign tourists. Therefore, it was noted that most of the routes of foreign travelers, the routes of their courageous journeys to explore the new world, have had a significant impact on the socio-economic development of the peoples of the world. For example, the opening and operation of the Great Silk Road, which united the continents of the world and the peoples of these continents in the 1st century BC, was celebrated by a famous Chinese intelligence officer, scientist, brave traveler and many others. associated with the name of Ambassador Zhang Xiang.

Yerik Raude (Malla) (950-1003). Almost from Columbus, who opened the New World

500 years ago, the Northern European Vikings discovered North America, and even lived there for some time. But in the 10th century, the Vikings' discovery remained unknown in the distant Greenland glaciers. In recent years, however, this historical fact has been somewhat clarified, with Scandinavian Vikings, including Yerik Raude, being the first Europeans to visit North America.

Idrisiy (1100-1165). Idrissy was born in Ceuta, Morocco. He traveled to Asia Minor when he was 16 years old. According to historians, Al-Idrisi was one of the first Arab scholars to travel

¹ Odiljon, G. (2021). Stages of combating corruption in the Republic of Uzbekistan. *Middle European Scientific Bulletin*, 8.

² Tolibjonovich, M. T. (2021). EASTERN RENAISSANCE AND ITS CULTURAL HERITAGE: THE VIEW OF FOREIGN RESEARCHERS. *ResearchJet Journal of Analysis and Inventions*, 2(05), 211-215.

throughout Europe and leave valuable information about the life of these countries in the 11th and 12th centuries. Due to Morocco's geographical proximity to Southwest Europe, the tourist made several trips to Portugal, France, England, Scotland, Ireland, and West Germany during the 1120s. The tourist also collected rich geographical information about Poland, Byzantium, the Balkan Peninsula, North Africa and some countries in Eastern Europe. He named more than 6,000 geographical objects in his texts and more than 2,500 in his attached maps.

The new era on geography began mainly in the middle of the eighteenth century. During this time, mankind reached the highest levels of its development and took courses to reach the next heights. However, lands that have not yet been inhabited by humans ("undiscovered reserves"), peoples and peoples, many natural environments, mountains and deserts and the climatic conditions of the planet, the mystery of flora and fauna . - There were a lot of synagogues. At the same time, although the means of transportation, tools, communication, and heavy loading of travels have been much improved by this time, the new travels of these times are based on the tools of life, purchases, and treats. and were brave scientists, famous people, who refused to live in the kingdom, and even knew that their lives would be in danger. That is why modern humanity remembers them and cherishes their memory.

The description of tourist routes in terms of historical and religious pilgrimage tourism takes into account the fact that these two types are interrelated. In fact, they are indistinguishable from each other. This is often due to tourist demand. More precisely, when international tourists visit religious shrines and shrines of religious leaders, they are also interested in the activities and history of this guide. Some tourist routes may require prayer facilities. In such cases, the guide-interpreter participating in the route must have a strong knowledge of history and experience in quickly creating the required conditions. Local tourists, on the other hand, are often only interested in the history of the pilgrimage. A booklet on the development of historical and religious tourist routes, a very interesting and brief information about the place of religious pilgrimage and the historical periods of its formation in the itinerary will certainly be of interest to tourists.

It is important to note that each tourist resource has its own history. When designing tourist routes for all types of tourism, the tour operator must find an answer to this question on the route. That is why the naming and designation of the theme of tourist routes is mainly called the name of the tourist resource - the place. For example, it is known that the routes designed by the Registan ensemble, Shahizinda or Amir Temur's hut are named after these historical monuments.

On these routes, some tourists (mostly Muslims) make the pilgrimage first and recite prayers from the verses of the Qur'an. He may later be interested in the history of this shrine. The second type of tourists (non-Muslims) first visit this tourist destination and then become interested in its history.

Routes of foreign travelers were also considered relative. Because, chet it is also impossible to cite all the travels of the fifty travelers. Therefore for both the most popular routes of foreign travelers, their new world The world of travel routes made with the courage to explore have had a significant impact on the socio-economic development of their peoples taken into account. For example, the continents of the world, the peoples living on these continents the opening of the Great Silk Road in the 1st century BC; a man who has been active for centuries, a famous Chinese spy, the name of Zhang Xiang, a scientist, a brave traveler, and an ambassador to many countries related to Willem Barends (1550 - 1597). Great geographical discoveries of the 15th-16th centuries to the beginning of the colonial phase, between European countries led to competition and struggle for new lands.

The result is the idea of finding a North Sea route to China and India at that time it seemed to be a kind of competition among seafarers gone. But the North Sea is covered in ice all year round, and that's it experienced that ships of the time could not withstand the compression of the ice the sailors knew very well. But V. Barents made this dangerous journey dared to increase. In 1594 he organized the first expedition to the North. On this journey he sailed to 77 degrees North latitude and was forced to turn back it has been. In 1595, V. Barents commissioned a third expedition on behalf of the Dutch government. It was formed in 1596 and extends 80 degrees north latitudes mapped all the lands, islands, and glaciers that existed. On a trip Barents and many of his sailors were killed. A brave traveler the name was immortalized and the former Murmansk Sea was renamed the Barents Sea. The geographical research of the new period is mainly from the second half of the eighteenth century started. In these times, humanity has reached a much higher level of development were the times when he climbed and began to climb to the next peak. However, lands that have not yet been inhabited ("undiscovered reserves"), peoples and peoples, many natural regions, mountains and deserts, and the climate of the planet properties, flora and fauna was too much. However, by this time the transport of travel, tools, means of communication with them, rescuing them in difficult situations. Although the possibilities of staying in these periods are much improved travelers from everything in their lives to new discoveries, renounced opportunities, luxuries and royal life, even the bravest scientists, who knew that their lives would be in danger were people. That is why modern humanity remembers them preserves and cherishes his memory.

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